

Kinetic Studies of the Formation of Dithizone. Part-I. Alkali assisted Conversion of Phenylhydrazinium Phenylhydrazine Dithiocarbamate and Diphenylthiocarbazide

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The kinetics of formation of dithizone (3) from phenylhydrazirium phenylhydrazine dithiocarbamate (1) and from phenylthiocarbazide (2) has been studied. The synthetic aspect of the formation of dithizone from phenylhydrazine and carbon disulphide has also been worked out. A mechanism for the formation of dithizone from 1 and 2 has been proposed.

EMIL Fischer¹ synthesised dithizone for the first time by a three-step process. The first step involved the condensation of phenylhydrazine with carbon disulphide giving a white salt (1) which on heating gave diphenylthiocarbazide (2). The oxidation of 2 resulted in the formation of dithizone (3). Bamberger² synthesised 3 by a different route starting from nitromethane and benzenediazonium chloride. During the last fifty years dithizone has occupied an unique position among organic analytical reagents. Its structure has been established during the seventies³.

The present paper deals with a study of the synthesis of dithizone by adopting Fischer's method and elucidation of mechanism of its formation by kinetic studies.

Experimental

Synthesis of phenylhydrazine dithiocarbamate (1) : In a two-necked flask fitted with a condenser and a dropping funnel containing a solution of pure redistilled phenylhydrazine (12.8 ml, 1.3 mol) in ether (600 ml), carbon disulphide (5.2 ml, 0.86 mol) was added with stirring. After the mixture was stirred for an additional 30 min, the white precipitate was filtered and washed with ether. Crystallisation from alcohol gave the pure compound (14 g, 80%), m.p. 80°; λ_{\max} 258 and 307 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 450, 3 120, 2 900, 2 650, 1 600, 1 500, 1 410, 1 340, 1 190 and 1 080 cm^{-1} .

Synthesis of phenylthiocarbazide (2) : 1 was transferred to a beaker and heated on a water-bath with stirring. After 10-15 min, the material softened and hydrogen sulphide gas was evolved. On further heating for about 30 min, ammonia gas was evolved. To the cooled mass, absolute ethanol (15 ml) was added and then warmed with stirring until the mass converted to granular form. After keeping for 1 h at room temperature the precipitate was filtered and washed with absolute ethanol.

The intermediate could not be crystallised from any solvent owing to its facile conversion to dithizone (70%), m.p. 150°.

Synthesis of dithizone (3) : It was synthesised by Billman's method⁴, m.p. 168°; ν_{\max} 1, 590, 1 500, 1 460, 1 438, 1 320, 1 215 and 1 145 cm^{-1} , m/e , 256, 150, 105, 93, 77 and 169.

Kinetic methods : Absorbance measurements were made in a Beckman 35 double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer equipped with matched quartz cells (1 cm). Values of absorbance were recorded at 480 nm for aquo-organic solvent system and at 470 nm for aqueous system. Cryostat-MK 70 was used for measuring the kinetics at 20°. All aqueous solutions were prepared using double-distilled water. All chemicals used were of reagent grade.

To the weighed amount of the substrate, the solvent (20 ml) which was kept at 20° for 30 min, was added. At regular intervals of time, aliquots of the solution was pipetted out, quenched and the O.D. measured. All the data recorded are an average of three to four sets of readings.

Thermal analysis : 2 (50 mg) was taken in a dry round-bottomed flask and heated at 120° ($\pm 5^\circ$) for 1 h in an oil-bath under low pressure. The product was cooled and dissolved in chloroform (50 ml). Absorbance was measured at 605 nm (3; λ_{\max} (CHCl_3) 605 nm, ϵ_{\max} 41.4×10^4)⁵, from which the percentage of 3 in the product was calculated to be 20%.

To the chloroform solution, dry hydrochloride gas was passed. It was then shaken with water to solubilise the hydrochloride formed and the water layer separated. Since the aqueous layer was coloured, the dye test for aniline could not be performed. So the aqueous layer was basified and the base extracted with ether. Ether was evaporated out and the dye test was performed successfully for aniline.

Results

Phenylhydrazine on condensation with carbon disulphide in ether in cold under continuous stirring gave a white crystalline salt (1, m.p. 98°). The salt (1) on heating and further work up with ethanol gave a white substance (2, m.p. 150°). On treatment with alkali, dithizone is formed from 2 as yellow anion (λ_{max} 470 nm, ϵ 22 000) in good yield (Chart 1).

Chart 1

In view of the fact that 1 gets converted to 3 in presence of alkali, the kinetics of this conversion has been investigated spectrophotometrically at 470 nm in acetone-water medium. To avoid the possibility of formation of hydrazone, alkali in acetone was added to 1. No hydrazone was formed even within 1 h of addition. The rate of conversion to dithizone was found to depend on the alkali concentration (Table 1). A plot of the rate constant vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ appeared as a straight line passing through the origin. pH of the solution however was not changed during the reaction. Therefore, the conversion of 1 to 3 is an alkali-catalysed process. This was also evident from the fact that varying the ratio of $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{1}]$ from 1 : 20 to 1 : 1, the nature of

TABLE 1—ALKALI DEPENDENCE OF RATE FOR CONVERSION OF 1 TO 3

$10^3[\text{1}] = 15.0 \text{ M}$, temp. = 20°, acetone - $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 94\%$ (v/v)			
$10^3[\text{OH}^-]$	$[\text{OH}^-] : [\text{1}]$	10^3 k min^{-1}	$10^5 \text{ k}/10^3[\text{OH}^-]$
0.80	1 : 20	0.99	1.24
1.67	1 : 10	2.73	1.58
3.35	1 : 5	4.88	1.5
5.31	1 : 3	8.69	1.74
10.3	1 : 1.5	10.91	1.10
16.0	1 : 1	26.8	1.63

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE OF CONVERSION OF 1 TO 3 ON [T-x-100] IN WATER

$[\text{OH}^-] = 5.3 \times 10^{-2}$, $[\text{1}] = 0.989 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, temp. = 20°										
[T-x-100]	0	0.1	0.2	0.6	0.7	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.33	1.42
10^5 k min^{-1}	9.5	19.8	27.0	34.3	42.0	34.0	34.6	34.0	34.5	35.0

TABLE 4—ALKALI DEPENDENCE OF RATE OF CONVERSION (1→3) IN WATER

$[\text{T-x-100}] = 1.11 \text{ v\%}$, $[\text{1}] = 0.989 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, temp. = 20°										
$10^3[\text{OH}^-]$	17.7	20.0	24.8	30.0	35.0	49.0	60.0	80.0	100.0	110.0
10^5 k min^{-1}	32.0	37.6	46.4	48.6	33.7	44.4	32.9	25.3	24.5	28.0

first order plot was not altered and the values of $10^5 \text{ k}/10^3 [\text{OH}^-]$ remained constant.

The rate dependence on the varying concentration of 1 was however complex. The rate constant was found to decrease rapidly within a short range of concentration of 1 and then remained asymptotic (Table 2). The values of $10^5 \text{ k} \times 10^3 [\text{1}]$ remained constant for the decreasing arm of the plot. If the concentration of 1 was decreased still further, the rate constant decreased substantially.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE OF CONVERSION OF 1 TO 3 ON [1]

$[\text{OH}^-] = 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, temp. = 20°, acetone - $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 94\%$ (v/v)		
$[\text{1}] \times 10^3$	10^5 k min^{-1}	
0.5	29.57	
1.0	14.58	
1.48	10.25	
1.98	4.94	
2.97	1.71	
3.96	1.49	
4.94	1.97	

The reaction has been studied by varying [1], alkali and a non-ionic surfactant, *i.e.* Triton X-100. The rate constant was found to increase to a constant value with increasing concentration of the surfactant (Table 3). The rate in Triton X-100 was found to increase with increasing concentration of alkali. A plot of rate constant vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ described a curve with a maximum at 0.05 M alkali (Table 4). The plot of rate constant vs [1], however, became a straight line passing through the origin (Table 5).

The rate of formation of dithizone from 2 has also been studied in DMSO- H_2O system. The rate of conversion of 2 was found to be substantially higher compared to the conversion of 1. The values of rate constant remained constant with varying $[\text{OH}^-]$ when $[\text{2}] : [\text{OH}^-]$ was 16-times or more but when $[\text{2}] : [\text{OH}^-]$ was 10-times or less, the rate constant was found to have a linear dependence on $[\text{OH}^-]$ the straight line passing through the origin (Table 6). pH of the solution did not change during the reaction. The rate constant was found to increase with increase of [2] (Table 7).

TABLE 5—DEPENDENCE OF RATE OF CONVERSION (1→3) ON [1] IN WATER

[T-X-100]=1.11 v%, [OH⁻]=3.5 × 10⁻², temp.=20°

10 ³ [1]	2.0	3.0	5.0	7.0	10.0
10 ⁶ k min ⁻¹	10.0	18.0	27.5	39.2	56.0

TABLE 6—ALKALI DEPENDENCE OF RATE OF CONVERSION (2→3)

Temp.=20°, DMSO-H₂O=50% (v/v)

[2]=10⁻³ M

10 ⁵ [OH ⁻]	2.0	3.0	4.0	4.8	5.0	6.0
10 ⁴ k min ⁻¹	9.9	9.0	9.2	12.25	12.3	12.5

[2]=10⁻⁴ M

10 ⁵ [OH ⁻]	1.0	2.0	3.0	5.0	8.0
10 ⁶ k min ⁻¹	5.75	9.9	15.17	41.9	67.0

TABLE 7—DEPENDENCE OF RATE OF CONVERSION (2→3) ON [2]

[OH⁻]=3 × 10⁻⁵ M, temp.=20°, DMSO-H₂O=50% (v/v)

10 ⁴ [2]	1.0	2.4	5.0	10.0
10 ⁶ k	15.2	21.8	28.9	90.8

Discussion

The present work is in agreement with the work of Fischer that the formation of dithizone from **1** is a two-step process. The intermediate **2** gets converted to **3** with a much faster rate than the conversion of **1** to **2** and hence the first step is the slow one. The ion pair (**1**) remain close because of coulombic attraction and the hydrogen bond formation (**4**). The OH⁻ attacks the acidic proton setting in a concerted electron flow leading to an unstable zwitterionic intermediate **5a**, which is in equilibrium with **5b**. This intermediate eliminates hydrogen sulphide easily to form **2** (Chart 2).

Chart 2

Increase of concentration of **1** may result in the formation of aggregates of ionic heads, thus reducing the probability of the approach of a hydroxide ion. This can be a rational explanation for the decrease of reaction rate with increasing concentration of **1**.

The decrease in rate by further decrease of [**1**] is, therefore, due to the concentration effect.

In order to study the effect of increasing [**1**] in a situation where aggregation of **1** could be avoided, was planned to study the reaction in micelles medium. Though the compound was soluble in CTAB, it gave viscous solution owing to the aggregation with surfactant ions. Therefore, the reaction has been studied in presence of a non-ionic surfactant, namely Triton X-100. Many workers^{6,7} have considered spherical structure for Triton X-100 micelles. Robson and Dennis⁸, however, have proposed an oblate rather than prolate micelle for Triton X-100. This view has also been further substantiated by small angle X-ray measurement⁹, conductivity and viscosity measurements¹⁰. As expected the rate constant increased with increasing [**1**]. The values of 10⁶k/10³ [**1**] remain constant. The reaction rate also increased to a constant value with increasing concentration of the surfactant. The rate increases by about 5 times, which may be due to the incorporation of **1** in the oxyethylene core.

The conversion of **2** to dithizone involves oxidation. Besides dithizone, aniline and phenylthiosemicarbazide are also formed¹¹. The experiment has been repeated and the formation of aniline has been observed. The mechanism (Chart 3) involves an initial attack of OH on the N-H proton resulting in a hydride shift to a neighbouring molecule and cleavage of a N-N bond. This is a situation akin to Cannizzaro reaction and Wolff-Kishner reduction.

Chart 3

The intermediate also is found to be converted to dithizone even in non-polar solvents and in the absence of alkali. The question that **2** might be converted to dithizone by aerial oxidation has been verified. The rate of conversion has been studied in nitrogen atmosphere also and no change in rate has been observed. The process of conversion from **2**, therefore is expected to be a symmetry-allowed process and should be thermally feasible one.

Hence, the intermediate was heated at 120° under low pressure⁹ for 1 h and about 20% conversion to dithizone has been noted.

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